

D1.19

Workpackage 1

Responsible Partner: University of
Surrey

GENERAL INFORMATION

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Other contributors	Written by Communications Team member Jennifer Cantlay. Reviewed by Project Management Team members.
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ANNUAL REPORT ON THE INTERNAL AND EXTERNAL NEWSLETTERS PRODUCED DURING THE FIFTH AND SIXTH YEARS

Overview: One Health EJP Newsletters

The One Health EJP produces two different newsletters throughout the year, the quarterly Consortium Newsletter and the bi-annual External Newsletter. These newsletters are created and disseminated by the Communications Team at the University of Surrey. The content of the newsletters is determined by the Communications Team with input from Consortium members and the Project Management Team (PMT). In the fifth and sixth years, the newsletters continued to be sent using MailChimp which allowed audiences to be monitored and updated when necessary, in accordance with the changes made to the Consortium members spreadsheet (for the Consortium and External newsletters) or online subscriptions via the form on the One Health EJP website (for the External Newsletter) and complies with GDPR. The internal mailing list had a maximum number of 1105 subscribers in the fifth and sixth years, during this period 24.3% (mean value) of subscribers opened the Consortium Newsletter when it was issued. The External newsletter had a maximum number of 1548 subscribers in the fifth and sixth years, during this period 36.7% (mean value) of subscribers opened the External Newsletter when it was issued. Additionally, MailChimp allows the Communications Team to monitor the links clicked in each newsletter and the number of people unsubscribing from the newsletter, these metrics inform the One Health EJP's Communication Strategy which is constantly evolving. MailChimp also integrates with Google Analytics and can track the traffic to the One Health EJP website from the newsletters.

The content and design of each newsletter is validated by the PMT before being sent. When the newsletters have been sent, they are also published on the One Health EJP website (<https://onehealthjep.eu/community/news/newsletters>) and shared on Twitter and LinkedIn.

Consortium Newsletters

In 2022, the Consortium Newsletters were sent out in March, June, September, and November. The final newsletter of 2022 was disseminated one month earlier than initially planned to avoid it being sent out in the same month as the external newsletter. In 2023, the Consortium Newsletters were sent out in February, May, and August. These newsletters targeted all One Health EJP Consortium members and were disseminated to the PMT, Institute Representative, Scientific Representatives, Programme Owner Representative, Programme Managers Committee members, Project Leaders, Project mailing lists, PhD students and supervisors, Communication Contact Persons network and stakeholders. Members were encouraged to disseminate the newsletters within their institutes. Although these newsletters were specifically targeted towards Consortium members, they did not contain any confidential information and therefore could be widely disseminated. For example, they were shared on the One Health EJP social media channels (Twitter and LinkedIn), posted on the Newsletters page of the One Health EJP website and published in One Health Commission's "One Health Happenings" newsletter.

The Consortium Newsletters followed a similar format and generally included the following sections:

- Key announcements.
- Key information.
- Collaboration and dissemination: events, updates from Work Packages, JRP, JIP and PhD projects.
- Publications and reports.
- Education and training programme news.

- “You may also be interested in” section that includes information on external conferences, events and online resources.
- Social media links to the One Health EJP Twitter and LinkedIn accounts.

This format was modified depending on the content available.

1. Consortium Newsletter March 2022

<https://mailchi.mp/519f350a0105/consortium-newsletter-march2022-14216292>

The key announcements section of this newsletter included:

- Promotion for the One Health EJP Annual Scientific Meeting (ASM) and ASM Satellite Workshop 2022 to be held in Italy in April 2022.
- Promotion for the OHEJP Dissemination Workshop on “Improving One Health preparedness to re(emerging) infectious threats” in March 2022.
- Information on the training workshops during March and April in preparation for the OHEJP SimEx conduction exercises in summer 2022.
- Information on the OHEJP Joint Integrative Project’s CARE, MATRIX, OH-HARMONY-CAP Joint Meeting on “Lessons learned and sustainability beyond 2022” in September 2022.
- Details of OHEJP participation in a side event "One Health European Joint Programme: lessons learnt from a European multidisciplinary initiative" at the OneEU2022 conference in June 2022.

The collaboration and dissemination section featured a variety of past events, project successes, including publications. More specifically:

- OHEJP contribution to the first dialogue meeting of the Partner Platform of the Regional One Health Coordination Mechanism (ROHCM) in November 2021.
- OHEJP participation and representation in the online event “Joining forces to escape the era of pandemic” by PREZODE initiative in February 2022.
- The OHEJP COVRIN project successfully held the "SARS-CoV2 in wildlife workshop" in February 2022.
- WP4 held the 4th Thematic Integrative Meeting on "Data sharing across disciplines" in February 2022.
- ANSES exhibitor participation in the Paris International Agricultural Show from 26th February to 6th March provided opportunity to disseminate information about the OHEJP to a wider external audience.
- Since JIP COVRIN conducts research on the on the detection and surveillance of SARS-CoV-2 in animal populations, the project provided formal response to a WHO/FAO/OIE joint statement recently delivered.
- Advertising the latest OHEJP IMPART project impact brochure to highlight the project’s outputs and outcomes.
- Sharing information about the new involvement of JRP TOXOSOURCES in “DISH Cluster” – a collaboration that aims to guide and support European consumers towards a safe and healthy diet.
- Informing Consortium members that the OHEJP Data Management Plans (DMPs) are available on the website.
- Four recent publications were listed from WP5 and projects of MedVetKlebs, MEmE and IMPART.

The education and training section shared the following announcements:

- The latest “OHEJP PhD Life” blog post by Ciriac Charles from PhD project PEMbo being available to read on the website.
- The three-minute thesis competition for PhD students to be held at the OHEJP ASM 2022.

- Extension of the deadline for the OHEJP Summer School 2022 to 31st March 2022.
- Extension of the deadline for the Short Term Missions 2002 to 31st March 2022.

Additionally, the key information section encouraged Consortium members to contact the Communications Team with details about upcoming event and project activities for dissemination. It also provided details of the Dissemination Information Pack available for Consortium members as a valuable resource to explain best practices for disseminating OHEJP news. An article requested Consortium members who had presented for the OHEJP at an event to complete a survey for keeping track of dissemination efforts.

As always, the “You may also be interested in” final section featured external news, and the footer of the newsletter included the One Health EJP hashtag and links to the One Health EJP’s website, Twitter and LinkedIn.

The MailChimp statistics for this newsletter were as follows:

Number of opens (the number of recipients who opened the campaign)	242/1104 (21.9%)
Total number of opens (the total number of times the campaign was opened by recipients. These counts includes multiple opens from individual recipient)	1146
Number of links clicked	52
Total number of clicks (total number of times links were clicked on by recipients. This counts includes multiple clicks from individual recipients)	269
Clicks per unique opens	21.5%

2. Consortium Newsletter June 2022

<https://mailchi.mp/860567bd6ba6/consortium-newsletter-june2022-15496057>

The key announcements section of this newsletter included:

- Celebrating the success of the One Health EJP Annual Scientific Meeting (ASM) in Orvieto, Italy as a hybrid event in April 2022. The article shared details of the conference programme, keynote speakers and audience participants (total numbers and demographics). Congratulations were extended to the ASM 2022 presentation winners with details of their projects and presentations.
- Promotion for the MATRIX Webinar Series 2022 on “Solutions for One Health Surveillance in Europe” from May 2022 onwards.
- Announcement about the OHEJP SimEx conduction of a National level One Health exercise occurring in participating countries for two days between May and July 2022.
- Announcement about the OHEJP participation in two side events at OneEU2022 conference: “Food Safety Knowledge Exchange (FSKX)” workshop on 20th June and “One Health EJP: Lessons learnt from a European multidisciplinary initiative” hybrid event on 22nd June 2022, with registration details provided.
- Information on the OHEJP Joint Integrative Project’s CARE, MATRIX, OH-HARMONY-CAP Joint Meeting on “Lessons learned and sustainability beyond 2022” in September 2022.
- Save the date for the OHEJP BIOPIGEE online workshop on “Biosecurity measures in primary pig production to control Salmonella and Hepatitis E virus” in September 2022.

The key information section focused on the publication of the One Health EJP Annual Report 2021 available on the website.

The collaboration and dissemination section featured the following outputs, activities, and events:

- Advertising the recent and existing OHEJP project impact brochures for TOX-Detect, IMPART and METASTAVA to highlight each project’s outputs and outcomes.
- Celebrating the success of the Dissemination Workshop on “Improving One Health Preparedness to (re) Emerging Infectious Threats” in March 2022 to highlight the wide audience participation.
- One Health EJP attended the Geneva Health Forum on 3rd to 5th May 2022 and participated in two workshops: “Time to rethink the science-policy interface? From COVID-19 lessons to strengthening One Health global policies” and “What training should we build for One Health / planetary health?”
- Sharing information about the recent involvement of JRP TOXOSOURCES in “DISH Cluster” collaboration and their online event in April 2022 to inform the public about food safety to avoid foodborne infectious hazards and on how to improve dietary habits.
- Details of the interview of One Health EJP Scientific Co-ordinator, Hein Imberechts, by Horizon magazine about antimicrobial resistance (AMR) in the article “The end of superbugs starts with better animal welfare.”
- Four recent publications were listed from projects of MEmE, OH-HARMONY-CAP, BIOPIGEE and ORION.

The education and training section provided the following highlights:

- Successful delivery of the ASM Satellite Workshop 2022 “Diagnostics workshop: mobile detection platforms for One Health diagnostics applications” with the final participant figure.
- An update on three Short Term Missions that have occurred during 2022 by PhD students Ingrid Cardenas Rey, Laura Gonzalez Villeta and Marieke de Cock from projects VIMOGUT, EnvDis and DESIRE, respectively, with five additional STM applications under review.
- Advertising the OHEJP CPD Module 2022 on “Rapid diagnostics and harmonisation of diagnostic tests” from 2nd to 4th November 2022.

As always, the “You may also be interested in” final section featured external news, and the the footer of the newsletter included the One Health EJP hashtag and links to the One Health EJP’s website, Twitter and LinkedIn.

The MailChimp statistics for this newsletter were as follows:

Number of opens (the number of recipients who opened the campaign)	216/1105 (19.5%)
Total number of opens (the total number of times the campaign was opened by recipients. These counts includes multiple opens from individual recipient)	574
Number of links clicked	38
Total number of clicks (total number of times links were clicked on by recipients. This counts includes multiple clicks from individual recipients)	110
Clicks per unique opens	17.6%

3. Consortium Newsletter September 2022

<https://mailchi.mp/45b7929579a2/consortium-newsletter-september2022-15522341>

The key announcements section of this newsletter included:

- A description of the highly successful OHEJP participation in two side events at OneEU2022 conference.
- The first OneEU2022 article focused on speakers' discussions at the "One Health EJP: Lessons learnt from a European multidisciplinary initiative" hybrid event on 22nd June 2022, which included a photo of the panel from the event. It provided links to two videos from the side event, one with the edited highlights and the other being the full video.
- The second article focused on "Food Safety Knowledge Exchange (FSKX)" workshop funded by JIP MATRIX on 20th June. It described how the workshop demonstrated the importance of predictive models and data analysis pipelines with the harmonised FSKX format, to promote its adoption by One Health professionals and modellers.
- Promotion for the MATRIX Webinar Series 2022 on "Solutions for One Health Surveillance in Europe" that was extended into October and November 2022.
- Advertising registration for the two OHEJP BIOPIGEE online workshops in September 2022 focused on "Biosecurity measures in primary pig production to control *Salmonella* and Hepatitis E virus" and "Biosecurity measures in slaughterhouses to control *Salmonella* and Hepatitis E virus."
- Reminder about the OHEJP Joint Integrative Project's CARE, MATRIX, OH-HARMONY-CAP Joint Meeting on "Lessons learned and sustainability beyond 2022" in September 2022.
- Sharing the dates for the Scientific Steering Board (SSB) Meeting to be held on 28th September 2022 and Programme Managers Committee (PMC) and Programme Owners Committee (POC) to be held on 21st and 22nd November 2022.

The key information section advertised the One Health External newsletter volume 7 and provided details about the website redevelopment and redesign.

The collaboration and dissemination section featured the following outputs, activities, and events:

- The successful delivery of OHEJP SimEx conduction of a National level One Health that occurred in 10 participating countries for two days between May and July, with the final exercise to be delivered in Belgium in September 2023.
- Promotion to stakeholders to use the One Health EJP Outcome Inventory (OHOI) – an online public database containing the Consortium's scientific and integrative results/activities, which is a valuable OHEJP dissemination tool.
- Reminder to read the existing OHEJP project impact brochures for TOX-Detect, IMPART and METASTAVA. Brochures are designed to appeal to a wide audience with bespoke infographics to illustrate the project topic to highlight outputs and outcomes.
- Four recent publications were listed from PhD projects WILBT, Codes4strains, PEMbo and ECO-HEN.

The education and training section provided the following highlights:

- The latest "OHEJP PhD Life" blog posts by Bosco Rodríguez Matamoros and Laura González Villeta shared their daily challenges and opportunities in working on their PhD projects METAPRO and EnvDis.
- An update on three newly completed Short Term Missions during 2022 by the following researchers: Emma Brook, Antonio Rodriguez and Ana Cristina Ferreira to benefit the projects BIOPIGEE, MATRIX and DISCOVER.
- Promoting registration for the OHEJP CPD Module 2022 on "Rapid diagnostics and harmonisation of diagnostic tests" from 2nd to 4th November 2022.

As always, the "You may also be interested in" final section featured external news, and the footer of the newsletter included the One Health EJP hashtag and links to the One Health EJP's website, Twitter and LinkedIn.

The MailChimp statistics for this newsletter were as follows:

Number of opens (the number of recipients who opened the campaign)	229/1088 21.0%
Total number of opens (the total number of times the campaign was opened by recipients. These counts includes multiple opens from individual recipient)	672
Number of links clicked	38
Total number of clicks (total number of times links were clicked on by recipients. This counts includes multiple clicks from individual recipients)	823
Clicks per unique opens	16.6%

4. Consortium Newsletter November 2022

<https://mailchi.mp/5d7dbd7e17a8/consortium-newsletter-november2022-15533937>

The key announcements section of this newsletter included:

- Promoting registration being open for the OHEJP Final School on the theme of “Sustainability in One Health: how can it be achieved?” to be held from 5th to 7th December 2022. The article described how this event would provide an impactful programme, with a variety of invited speakers from research, industry, government, science communications, policy, and education.
- Announcement of the OHEJP CPD Module 2022 on “Rapid diagnostics and harmonisation of diagnostic tests” being underway from 2nd to 4th November 2022. This article described how the module’s high quality training is provided by experts from JIPs of OH-HARMONY-CAP, MATRIX and CARE and the larger One Health domain.
- Promoting the additional MATRIX webinar on “What is special & common for foodborne hazards in One Health Surveillance?” to be held in December 2022 under the MATRIX Webinar Series 2022.
- Reminder about the Programme Managers Committee (PMC) and Programme Owners Committee (POC) being scheduled for 21st and 22nd November 2022. This article highlighted the importance of this meeting for disseminating OHEJP outcomes and the legacy process.
- Save the date for the Joint SimEx/Dissemination Workshop “A One Health Simulation Exercise as a roadmap for future foodborne outbreak preparedness” to be held on 6th December 2022.
- Promoting the JIP COVRIN final meeting to be held in Teramo, Italy during December 2022, as a hybrid event for all COVRIN project members across 16 partner institutions and invited stakeholders from key organisations.

The key information section requested input from project leaders, PhD students and supervisors for project information (outputs, outcomes and expected impacts) to update these webpages in relation to the website redevelopment and redesign work. An article also informed the Consortium that new member registration for OHEJP website would close by February 2023.

The collaboration and dissemination section featured the following outputs, activities, and events:

- An interview with COHESIVE project leader, Kitty Maassen, was published online by RIVM in October, with the link shared in the newsletter article. Kitty highlighted COHESIVE project’s achievements in developing key guidelines and IT tools for One Health approaches to signalling, assessing, and controlling zoonoses.

- Advertising the latest OHEJP LISTADAPT project impact brochure to highlight the project's outputs and outcomes.
- JRP TOXOSOURCES co-organised a breakfast session at European Health Forum Gastein EHFG2022 in September 2022 on “Co-creating better food systems in Europe” with the link to the YouTube video provided.
- Three recent publications were listed from projects BIOPIGEE, WORLDCOM and ADONIS.

The education and training section provided the following highlights:

- An update on three case studies from Short Term Missions completed during 2022 by the following PhD students: Ingrid Cardenas Rey (VIMOGUT) and Laura Gonzalez Villeta (EnvDis).

As always, the “You may also be interested in” final section featured external news, and the footer of the newsletter included the One Health EJP hashtag and links to the One Health EJP’s website, Twitter and LinkedIn.

The MailChimp statistics for this newsletter were as follows:

Number of opens (the number of recipients who opened the campaign)	263/1088 24.2%
Total number of opens (the total number of times the campaign was opened by recipients. These counts includes multiple opens from individual recipient)	935
Number of links clicked	55
Total number of clicks (total number of times links were clicked on by recipients. This counts includes multiple clicks from individual recipients)	690
Clicks per unique opens	20.9%

5. Consortium Newsletter February 2023

<https://mailchi.mp/e65f6993ea63/consortium-newsletter-february2023-15580062>

The key announcements section of this newsletter included:

- Registration open announcement for One Health EJP Conference 2023: Collaborating to face future One Health challenges in Europe to be held in June 2023. The article provides details of registration deadlines and highlights the wide target audience of departments and executive agencies of the European Commission; agencies of the European Union; One Health and other scientific initiatives; associations dealing with human, animal, and environmental health (private sector, citizen, farmers, or patients associations); general and specialised press.
- Announcement that OHEJP Sustainability Co-leader Dr Stefano Morabito from Istituto Superiore di Sanità (ISS) will be an invited speaker at the One Health Summit 2023 on 21st March, as organised by Bamberg Health.
- Promoting registration being open for the Scientific Steering Board (SSB) Meeting from 23rd to 24th March 2023 in Vienna.
- Save the date announcement for the OHEJP WP4 Dissemination Webinar "New tools for Surveillance and Risk Assessment" to be held on 28th March, as a demonstration of One Health EJP outputs.

The key information section included details of the ongoing website redevelopment and redesign. It informed members that new registration to the website would close by 31st March 2023. This section

promoted the importance of the recently updated One Health Outcome Inventory to benefit stakeholders across public health, animal health and food safety sectors.

The collaboration and dissemination section featured the following outputs, activities, and events:

- Celebrating the success of the Joint SimEx/Dissemination Workshop “A One Health Simulation Exercise as a roadmap for future foodborne outbreak preparedness” held on 6th December 2022. It highlighted the positive feedback from participants gained from a survey and provided a link to the report.
- Reminder to read the existing bespoke OHEJP project impact brochures for TOX-Detect, IMPART, METASTAVA and LISTADAPT, which highlight project outputs and outcomes. A short summary explained the content of each brochure was provided. Followed by a call out to project leaders to get in contact with Communications team members to create their own brochure.
- Highlighting the One Health EJP contributions to two external online training courses: “One Health Pandemic preparedness, prevention and response” modular course by Coursera and the “One Health module for IPA beneficiaries” introductory workshop co-organised by EFSA and the Med-Vet-Net Association. The involvement in these external courses widens the reach of OHEJP impact.
- Announcement for the “Analysis of outcomes and uptake of One Health EJP outputs by stakeholders” branded report by WP7 being available on the website.
- Four recent publications were listed from projects MoMIR-PPC, HME-AMR, DiSCoVer and FED-AMR.

The education and training section provided the following highlights:

- An update on two additional case studies from the Short Term Missions completed during 2022 by researchers Eve Zeyl Fiskebeck (for projects BeONE and DiSCoVer).
- Promoting the successes of three PhD students who have completed their doctoral research and passed their *viva voce* examinations.

As always, the “You may also be interested in” final section featured external news, and the footer of the newsletter included the One Health EJP hashtag and links to the One Health EJP’s website, Twitter and LinkedIn.

The MailChimp statistics for this newsletter were as follows:

Number of opens (the number of recipients who opened the campaign)	288/1072 26.9%
Total number of opens (the total number of times the campaign was opened by recipients. These counts includes multiple opens from individual recipient)	1413
Number of links clicked	74
Total number of clicks (total number of times links were clicked on by recipients. This counts includes multiple clicks from individual recipients)	1059
Clicks per unique opens	25.7%

6. Consortium Newsletter May 2023

<https://mailchi.mp/e318a18b1d4b/consortium-newsletter-may2023-15594978>

The key announcements section of this newsletter included:

- Reminder to register for online attendance to the One Health EJP Conference 2023: “Collaborating to face future One Health challenges in Europe” to be held 19th to 21st June 2023, as in person registration has closed. The article highlights the broad audience from public and private sector organisations across Europe who are welcome to attend this high-level event.
- Announcement about the “Workshop on the Institutionalisation of One Health” to be held during the afternoon of 21st June 2023 (after the One Health EJP Conference), with participation by email invitation only.
- Registration open announcement for the OHEJP WP6 Dissemination Webinar “New Tools for Detection and Surveillance” to be held on 9th June, which will present the implementation and application of project tools.
- Registration open announcement for One Health EJP Final Meeting to be held on 11th and 12th September 2023.

The key information section promoted the One Health EJP Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda (SRIA) being available as a branded report on the website. The links to a blog post about the SRIA and a downloadable SRIA flyer were provided. An update on the website redevelopment and redesign was given, as it is near completion.

The collaboration and dissemination section featured the following outputs, activities, and events:

- Advertising the newly available project impact brochures for ARDIG and FULL-FORCE describing their relevance to the issue of antimicrobial resistance. The article highlighted our dissemination strategy to these brochures to wider audiences via our social media platforms and inclusion on the One Health Commission’s newsletter.
- Sharing the success of the Scientific Steering Board (SSB) Meeting from 23rd to 24th March 2023 in Vienna and its input to the OHEJP legacy process.
- Celebrating the excellent attendance of over 120 people for the Dissemination Webinar on “New tools for Surveillance and Risk Assessment” on 28th March.
- An article describing the contribution of invited speaker, OHEJP Sustainability Co-leader Dr Stefano Morabito, at the One Health Summit 2023 on 21st March, as organised by Bamberg Health.
- Announcement to remind members to read the “Analysis of outcomes and uptake of One Health EJP outputs by stakeholders” available on the website.
- Four recent publications were listed from projects MATRIX, BIOPIGEE, NOVA and DiSCoVer.

The education and training section provided the following highlights:

- #OHEJPphdlife campaign to share the daily working lives of five PhD students, with the recent blog post by Elena Anedda working on HME-AMR project.
- Completion of ten Short Term Missions by researchers from across the Consortium. Information on the latest STM case study explaining the research by Sandrine Baron and Laetitia Le Devendec on antimicrobial resistance in aquatic environments.
- Celebrating the achievements of 17 OHEJP PhD students, with five students now passing their *viva voce* examinations and 12 students with authorship on publications in peer-reviewed journals.

As always, the “You may also be interested in” final section featured external news, and the footer of the newsletter included the One Health EJP hashtag and links to the One Health EJP’s website, Twitter and LinkedIn.

The MailChimp statistics for this newsletter were as follows:

Number of opens (the number of recipients who opened the campaign)	345/1031 33.5%
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Total number of opens (the total number of times the campaign was opened by recipients. These counts includes multiple opens from individual recipient)	1074
Number of links clicked	70
Total number of clicks (total number of times links were clicked on by recipients. This counts includes multiple clicks from individual recipients)	2031
Clicks per unique opens	20.3%

7. Consortium Newsletter August 2023

<https://mailchi.mp/36afa035438d/consortium-newsletter-august2023-15607214>

The key announcements section of this newsletter included:

- Announcement that this is the final Consortium newsletter prior to the end of the programme on 30th September.
- Celebrating the success of the One Health EJP Stakeholder Conference 2023: “Collaborating to face future One Health challenges in Europe” held as a hybrid event in Brussels from 19th to 21st June 2023. The article provided attendance figures for the conference and summarised the varied range of topics shared with the broad audience.
- An article described the interactive “Workshop on the Institutionalisation of One Health” held on 21st June 2023, after the One Health EJP Stakeholder Conference, with the preparation of a roadmap document post event.
- A reminder about registering for the One Health EJP Final Meeting to be held on 11th and 12th September 2023, as a special event of celebration and commemoration.
- Announcement about the 4th Dissemination Workshop on “Communication, education and training, and science to policy translation: Lessons learnt and legacy of the One Health EJP” will be made available as webinar, to be shared on our digital platforms and website in September 2023.

The first article in the key information section provided an announcement of the One Health EJP Annual Report 2022 being available on our website. A subsequent article gave the latest news on the Bilateral Discussions with stakeholders from seven key external European and global organisations. Another article explained that the website will be handed over to the Med-Vet-Net Association for the start of October 2023 for long-term sustainability of the digital resources. This section also promoted the “One Health EJP Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda (SRIA)” and “Analysis of outcomes and uptake of One Health EJP outputs by stakeholders” both being available as branded reports on the website, with links the documents provided.

The collaboration and dissemination section featured the following outputs, activities, and events:

- Advertising the six Project Impact Brochures are available on our website, with MATRIX brochure coming soon. A summary of each brochure was provided to explain the relevance of each project’s outputs and outcomes for One Health.
- Celebrating the good attendance at the Dissemination Webinar on New Tools for Detection and Surveillance organised by WP6 and held on 9th June 2023.
- An article describing the contribution of senior One Health EJP members representing the Consortium at four recent external events held in Brussels, Sweden and two online.
- Four recent publications were listed from projects ADONIS, OH-HARMONY-CAP, OHEJP SimEx and WP5.

The education and training section provided the following information:

- #OHEJPhdlife campaign to share the daily working lives of six PhD students, with the recent blog post by Ingrid Cárdenas Rey from VIMOGUT project.
- Completion of ten Short Term Missions case studies by researchers from across the Consortium. Information on the latest STM case study explaining the research by Bosco Rodríguez Matamoros to conduct laboratory work focused on AMR for his PhD project METAPRO.
- Celebrating the achievements of 17 OHEJP PhD students, with six students now awarded their doctorates, 12 students with authorship on 29 publications in peer-reviewed journals.
- Three recent publications were listed from PhD projects: ToxSauQMRA, SUSTAIN and HME-AMR.

As always, the “You may also be interested in” final section featured external news, and the footer of the newsletter included the One Health EJP hashtag and links to the One Health EJP’s website, Twitter and LinkedIn.

The MailChimp statistics for this newsletter were as follows:

Number of opens (the number of recipients who opened the campaign)	233/1021 22.8%
Total number of opens (the total number of times the campaign was opened by recipients. These counts includes multiple opens from individual recipient)	813
Number of links clicked	44
Total number of clicks (total number of times links were clicked on by recipients. This counts includes multiple clicks from individual recipients)	2463
Clicks per unique opens	18.9%

8. Overview of Statistics for Consortium Newsletters

Overall, the number of Consortium members opening the newsletter during the fifth and sixth years is between 20-33%, the maximum of this range was higher than for year three (21-27%) and year four (20-22%). According to MailChimp the average number of opens for a newsletter should be between 15-25%, therefore these newsletters are performing as expected and some newsletter editions have performed higher than expected. The Communications Team had worked on trying to improve the statistics by making the newsletter content more visually appealing with photos and bespoke images. The June 2022 edition newsletter had the lowest numbers of interactions, which may be attributed its delivery at the end of June, when Consortium members at academic institutes could already be on summer vacation.

External Newsletters

In 2022, two External Newsletters were published in June and December, and one External Newsletter was published in May 2023. The Communications Team previously redesigned the style and format of the newsletter to a magazine style in 2021 and this approach has been successful to increase engagement from the OHEJP global audience. This magazine style of this newsletter was created in InDesign by the Communications team, and produced as a pdf that was uploaded to our website. Recipients were in receipt of a placeholder image, sent via MailChimp to enable data gathering, that lead them to the uploaded interactive pdf. Therefore, with the External Newsletters, it is only possible to see the number of opens and clicks of the image, not the individual links in the newsletters (unlike the Consortium Newsletter where this information can be made available). These design changes have been important in increasing audience engagement during the final two years of the programme when

the One Health EJP has needed to disseminate more scientific outputs and outcomes from completion of JIPs and JRPs.

The External Newsletter audience included:

- The general public.
- Scientists external to the One Health EJP.
- Stakeholders.
- Individuals that have subscribed to the One Health EJP mailing list via the website.

All website visitors and social media followers can join this mailing list. There were 1521 subscribers to the External Newsletter(s) (as of 04/09/23). This newsletter was also disseminated to the One Health EJP internal mailing list.

1. External Newsletter June 2022

https://onehealthjep.eu/wp-content/uploads/2022/06/OHEJPEXternalNewsletter_vol7_June2022.pdf

The main article on the first page titled “One Health research showcased in Italy” reported on the Annual Scientific Meeting 2022 held as a hybrid event in Orvieto, Italy. It highlighted the attendance from a large international audience and the varied scientific programme, which included oral presentations, poster sessions, roundtable discussion and the 3-minute thesis competition. The side article on the first page described the One Health EJP SimEx conduction exercises occurring across participating European countries during the summer 2022. The SimEx project enables cross-sector collaboration for conducting a disease outbreak scenario focused on a foodborne zoonosis.

On the second page, the main article provided details of the existing Project Impact Brochures, from METASTAVA, IMPART and TOX-Detect projects. These dissemination tools are produced by the OHEJP Communications team to showcase key messages and outcomes from Joint Integrative and Joint Research Projects to a wide audience of both scientists and non-scientists. The second article on this page advertised the recent publication of the Annual Report for 2021.

Four articles were featured on the third page of the newsletter. The first article titled “Translating science to policy through dissemination workshops” described the purpose of these workshops to disseminate solutions developed by joint integrative/research projects to policy and decision makers across Europe. Further details were provided about the impactful recent workshop on “Improving One Health Preparedness to (re) Emerging Infectious Threats” held in March 2022. The second article promoted the “#OHEJPphdlife” campaign, launched in 2021, to share a day in the life of individual PhD students and their research activities. These blog posts provide an insight into the daily opportunities and challenges faced by OHEJP PhD students, with great engagement on the subsequent social media posts. The third article focused on the successful online ASM Satellite Workshop 2022: Diagnostics workshop on mobile detection platforms for One Health diagnostics applications. A final short article celebrated the achievements of the three OHEJP ASM 2022 winners Marieke de Cock, Olivia Turner and Ulrike Binsker.

Finally, the fourth page showcased the MATRIX webinars to advance One Health Surveillance scheduled from May to November 2022, as organised by Statens Serum Institut. The article highlighted how this webinar series provides an exciting training activity to deliver the latest information on implementing OHEJP MATRIX solutions to surveillance officers, researchers, and managers from European institutes. The last section of the newsletter announced the upcoming activities of 2022: OHEJP involvement in two side events at the ONE2022 Conference in June 2022, MATRIX webinar series, OHEJP BIOPIGEE Workshop, OHEJP CARE, MATRIX, OH-HARMONY-CAP Joint and

individual project meetings, and the OHEJP CPD Module 2022 on Rapid diagnostics and harmonisation of diagnostic tests.

The MailChimp statistics for this newsletter were as follows:

	June 2022 External newsletter subscribers.
Number of opens (number of recipients who opened the campaign)	570/1548 36.8%
Total number of opens (total number of times the campaign was opened by recipients)	1135
Number of links clicked	221
Total number of clicks (total number of times links were clicked on by recipients. This counts includes multiple clicks from individual recipients)	602
Clicks per unique opens	38.8%

2. External Newsletter December 2022

https://onehealthjep.eu/wp-content/uploads/2022/12/OHEJPEXternalNewsletter_vol8_Dec2022-final.pdf

The first page featured an article on the OHEJP Final School 2022, held as an online event on 5th to 7th December 2022 with the theme of “Sustainability in One Health – how can it be achieved?” as organised and hosted by the University of Surrey. This international educational event was extremely well-attended with participants from across the world, including a wide variety of speakers from the OHEJP and external organisations.

The second page presented an article on the Programme Managers Committee (PMC) and Programme Owners Committee (POC) joint meeting held at the Public Health Agency of Sweden (FoHM) in Stockholm during November 2021. It explained how this joint meeting strengthened relationships between Consortium members and external stakeholders to ensure the One Health EJP legacy in future OH activities across Europe.

The third page featured three articles focused on research project and training outcomes. The first article described the BIOPIGEE Workshop on “Biosecurity measures to control *Salmonella* and HEV along the pig production chain in Europe” held in September 2022. This had high attendance numbers by international participants with varied professional backgrounds, The second article described the interview with COHESIVE project leader, Kitty Maassen, published online in October 2022 by the National Institute of Public Health and the Environment (RIVM), the Netherlands, and shared the link. It highlighted the importance of COHESIVE’s work to develop tools used in integrated risk analysis systems to improve European preparedness for future zoonosis events. The third article celebrated the success of the final CPD Module on “Rapid diagnostics and harmonisation of diagnostic tests” held as a hybrid training event in November 2022 and hosted by the Technical University of Denmark’s National Food Institute (DTU Food) and Statens Serum Institut (SSI) in Copenhagen. This module shared the experiences and new scientific knowledge from 3 OHEJP Joint Integrative Projects: OH-Harmony-CAP, MATRIX and CARE.

The fourth page provided an article describing six Short Term Missions (STMs) successfully conducted during 2022, with four further STMs underway. These STMs demonstrate the scientific expertise, methodologies, equipment, and facilities that were shared to harmonise existing One Health approaches and facilitate collaborations. The last section of the newsletter announced the upcoming activities for 2023: OHEJP Scientific Steering Board Meeting in Vienna during March 2023, OHEJP Stakeholder Conference in June 2023 and the OHEJP Final Meeting in Paris during September 2023.

The MailChimp statistics for this newsletter were as follows:

	December 2022 External newsletter subscribers.
Number of opens (number of recipients who opened the campaign)	522/1538 33.9%
Total number of opens (total number of times the campaign was opened by recipients)	1200
Number of links clicked	148
Total number of clicks (total number of times links were clicked on by recipients. This counts includes multiple clicks from individual recipients)	401
Clicks per unique opens	28.4%

3. External Newsletter May 2023

https://onehealthjep.eu/wp-content/uploads/2023/05/OHEJPEXternalNewsletter_Vol_9_04-May2023.pdf

The article on the first page was an announcement on the upcoming One Health EJP Conference 2023 for stakeholders on “Collaborating to face future One Health challenges in Europe” to be held in June 2023. It aimed to encourage a wide variety of professionals from private and public sector organisations to register for online attendance, since in-person registration had closed. A side article described the main conference themes in more detail, with a link to the conference website.

The second page included articles that focused on our wider dissemination and engagement activities. The first one detailed the recent external engagement activities, including OHEJP contribution to two external One Health courses, our representation at the One Health Summit 2023 in Brussels, and delivery of the OHEJP Dissemination Webinar on “New tools for Surveillance and Risk Assessment.” This was followed by a summary of the successful Joint One Health EJP SimEx/Dissemination Workshop: “A One Health Simulation Exercise as a roadmap for future foodborne outbreak preparedness” held in December 2022. The article provided a quote from Anna Omazic, One Health EJP SimEx Project Leader and links to the blog post and full report of the event.

On the third page, three short articles focused on research outputs, outcomes, and recent reports. The leading article promoted two new reports “Analysis of outcomes & uptake of One Health EJP outputs by stakeholders” and “Final One Health Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda (SRIA) 2021 – 2030” being available on the website. This was followed by information about the latest Project Impact Brochure on FULL-FORCE, which has been added to the growing brochure collection of TOX-Detect, IMPART, METASTAVA and LISADAPT for ensuring the legacy of OHEJP research. Updates to the One

Health EJP Outcome Inventory (OHOI) were also shared with a quote by Ludovico Sepe, the One Health EJP Science to Policy Advisor, on how best to access this online database.

On the final page, education and training activities were covered by two articles. The first one celebrated PhD student achievements, by naming the five students featured in the “#OHEJPphdlife” campaign and the four students who had successfully passed their *viva voce* examinations. The main article provided an update on the three case studies from recent Short Term Missions conducted by researchers, Eve Zeyl Fiskebeck, Carlos Sacristán Yagüe, Sandrine Baron and Laetitia Le Devendec.

The last section of the newsletter announced the upcoming activities for 2023: OHEJP Dissemination Webinar “New Tools for Detection and Surveillance” in June 2023, One Health EJP Conference 2023 for stakeholders in June 2023 and the OHEJP Final Meeting in Paris during September 2023.

The MailChimp statistics for this newsletter were as follows:

	May 2023 External newsletter subscribers.
Number of opens (number of recipients who opened the campaign)	590/1492 39.5%
Total number of opens (total number of times the campaign was opened by recipients)	1249
Number of links clicked	272
Total number of clicks (total number of times links were clicked on by recipients. This counts includes multiple clicks from individual recipients)	1396
Clicks per unique opens	46.1%

4. Overview of Statistics for External Newsletters

Overall, the number of readers from the external mailing list opening the newsletter is between 34-40%, which has improved on the statistics in the third year but is lower than the statistics in the fourth year. This suggests that the new and improved design (from the fourth year onwards) is more engaging for our audiences, although the novelty of the design has reduced audience interest over time (during the fifth and sixth years). According to MailChimp the average number of opens for a newsletter should be between 15-25%, therefore these newsletters are performing higher than expected.

5. Additional Newsletters

Two additional short newsletters disseminated in March 2023 to promote registration for the One Health EJP Conference 2023 for stakeholders. The first delivered on the 8th of March 2023 was an announcement for conference registration being open, providing details of both in-person and online participation, with links to the website and conference agenda. The campaign URL was <https://mailchi.mp/615f69820b2c/one-health-ejp-conference-june2023-15582178>

The second delivered was an announcement about the extension to in-person registration for the conference 24th March 2023. The campaign URL was <https://mailchi.mp/4e4cea1c24cc/one-health-ejp-conference-june2023-15586606>

They were sent as emails to our newsletter audiences and they were not uploaded to our website.

The MailChimp statistics for these newsletters were as follows:

	8th March conference newsletter.	24th March conference newsletter.
Number of opens (number of recipients who opened the campaign)	608/1509 40.3%	648/1490 43.5%
Total number of opens (total number of times the campaign was opened by recipients)	2390	4087
Number of links clicked	257	297
Total number of clicks (total number of times links were clicked on by recipients. This counts includes multiple clicks from individual recipients)	1474	2056
Clicks per unique opens	42.3%	45.8%

One additional newsletter was disseminated in June 2023 as an announcement about the Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda (SRIA) being available on the website. This provided a link to the full branded document and a summary flyer to promote the contents of the SRIA. This short newsletter was disseminated on 7th June 2023. This was sent as an email to our newsletter audiences and it was not uploaded to our website.

The campaign URL was <https://mailchi.mp/b91e7b7ca25d/one-health-ejp-sria-june2023-15597458>

The MailChimp statistics for this newsletter were as follows:

	7th June SRIA newsletter.
Number of opens (number of recipients who opened the campaign)	585/1486 39.4%
Total number of opens (total number of times the campaign was opened by recipients)	1362
Number of links clicked	237
Total number of clicks (total number of times links were clicked on by recipients. This counts includes multiple clicks from individual recipients)	2204
Clicks per unique opens	40.5%

Future Newsletters

Since the OHEJP finishes on 30th September 2023, there will be no further newsletters after this date.